

Studies in Formation and Properties of Carbon-Sulphur Surface Complexes. Part VI. Formation of Complexes on Carbon Blacks

BALWANT RAI PURI, DARSHAN KUMAR and B. C. KAISTHA

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-14

Manuscript received 8 April 1972; revised 27 August 1972; accepted 23 April 1973

Interaction of carbon blacks with sulphur, carbon disulphide and hydrogen sulphide at elevated temperatures results in appreciable fixation of sulphur, the optimum temperature for maximum fixation being 600° in each case. There are strong indications that sulphur is fixed through chemical bonding and is not held as a polymer in the micropores. The results also indicate that the fixation involves addition of sulphur at the unsaturated sites as well as at certain active centres forming stable carbon-sulphur bonds, and substitution of phenolic and quinonic groups initially present on the surface yielding thiophenolic and thioquinonic structures.

THE formation of highly stable carbon-sulphur surface complexes on sugar and coconut charcoals, by reacting them with sulphur vapour, carbon disulphide, hydrogen sulphide and sulphur dioxide, were reported in previous publications^{1,2}. The mechanism of such fixations of sulphur, however, was not substantiated. Some workers³, in the meanwhile, have expressed the view that this sulphur is not truly chemically combined to the surface but is held as a polymer in the micropores of charcoal. It was thought of interest, therefore, to extend this work to carbon blacks which are essentially non-porous or contain micropores which are too small⁴ to be accessible to sulphur polymer. The present work relates to fixation of sulphur on carbon blacks on treatment with sulphur vapour, carbon disulphide vapour and hydrogen sulphide under optimum conditions and to explore possible mechanisms involving such fixations.

Experimental

Materials and Methods: A few samples of well known carbon blacks having different specific surface areas and hydrogen and oxygen contents were used before as well as after outgassing at 700° and 1000°.

The reaction with sulphur was carried out by mixing 5 g. carbon (dried at 120°) with 15 g. of sulphur (C.P.) in a small pestle and mortar and heating in a tube furnace (15"×1") at different temperatures upto 800° for a known interval of time. Hydrogen sulphide was evolved in the process and was estimated iodometrically. The amount was found to be within the limits of the hydrogen content of the carbon black concerned.

The reactions with carbon disulphide and hydrogen sulphide were carried out in the manner described earlier in the case of similar experiments with charcoals^{1,2}. Some of the carbon blacks were also treated

with aqueous hydrogen sulphide. This was done by mixing 1 g. carbon black with 300 ml. of 0.15 *N* hydrogen sulphide and shaking the suspension at ordinary temperature for 4 days. The products obtained from each treatment were extracted with carbon disulphide in a Soxhlet extractor for 12 days (8 hr a day) to remove any adhering or physically adsorbed sulphur. The final products were dried in an air-oven at 120° and stored in well stoppered bottles flushed with nitrogen. The sulphur content of each product was estimated by treating 0.5 g. in a current of hydrogen at 900° and estimating the amount of hydrogen sulphide evolved iodometrically. The replicates agreed within less than 1 per cent. The method was checked with Escka's method⁵ in a number of cases. The agreement was within less than half per cent.

Description of sulphur: A known weight (1 g.) of each sulphurized product was taken in a platinum boat and heated electrically to a desired temperature upto 1000° in a silica tube (24"× $\frac{3}{4}$ ") in a current of nitrogen (@ 2.5 l/hr). The combined sulphur was found to come off, at temperatures above 600°, partly as free sulphur, hydrogen sulphide and carbon disulphide. The amount of each was estimated as described before⁶.

Sodium azide-iodine reaction: Sodium azide-iodine reaction evolving nitrogen

was studied by mixing 0.1 g. of a sulphurized product with 20 ml. of 0.05 *M* iodine containing 130 milligrams of sodium azide. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating nitrogen evolved at different intervals of time⁷. The maximum amount of nitrogen expected theoretically was 67.2 ml. (N.T.P.).

Results and Discussion

The results of a few preliminary experiments which were carried out with one of the carbon blacks (Mogul-A) for standardising optimum conditions for getting maximum fixation of sulphur are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2. It is seen that each treatment with

Fig. 1.

Effect of temperature on fixation of sulphur by Mogul-A on treatment with sulphur (○—○), carbon disulphide (●—●) and hydrogen sulphide (▲—▲).

each reagent yields the desired results if carried out at 600° for 4 hr. The fall in the fixation of sulphur beyond 600° appears to be due to thermal instability of the surface complex, as will be shown later in this paper. In all subsequent experiments, the reactions were carried out under the optimum conditions mentioned above.

Fig. 2.

Effect of time of treatment at 600° on fixation of sulphur by Mogul-A on interaction with sulphur (○—○), carbon disulphide (●—●) and hydrogen sulphide (▲—▲).

The amounts of sulphur fixed on the various carbon blacks, before as well as after outgassing at 700° and 1000°, on treatment with various reagents under optimum conditions, are recorded in Table 1. It is seen, in the first instance, that the amount of sulphur fixed varies with the nature of the reagent used,

the value being maximum when treatment is given with sulphur and minimum when treatment is given with hydrogen sulphide. Since in the case of treatment with sulphur, some hydrogen sulphide was also evolved, as already mentioned, this treatment, in fact, amounts to joint treatment with sulphur vapour and hydrogen sulphide. This may be one of the reasons for greater fixation of sulphur in this treatment. It is interesting to note that although carbon blacks are essentially non-porous, yet an appreciable amount of sulphur is fixed in each case. Voet, Lamond and Sweigart⁴ who studied the porosity of the various carbon blacks found Mogul-A alone to be porous. The size of the pores, however, was largely restricted to be within 5.5 Å diameter. This size, evidently, is much smaller than that of the sulphur polymer, S₈. It appears that sulphur atoms, produced at 600°, through the action of hydrogen, liberated from the carbon blacks, with sulphur vapour existing as S₂ at that temperature,

or through the partial decomposition of carbon disulphide or hydrogen sulphide, get chemisorbed at certain suitable sites on the carbon surface yielding stable carbon-sulphur surface complexes.

There seems to be no obvious relationship between surface area (column 2) and the amount of sulphur fixed. There is, for example, an appreciable decrease in the amount of sulphur fixed when a carbon black is outgassed at 700° or above, even though the magnitude of surface area undergoes only a minor change. Since the oxygen and hydrogen contents undergo a distinct fall on evacuation⁵, it appears quite likely that fixation of sulphur is, in part, due to interaction with hydrogen, oxygen or oxy-hydrogen groups on the carbon surface.

It was interesting to note that bromine value as a measure of surface unsaturation⁹ which was appreciable before fixation of sulphur fell to zero in every case. Thus, the unsaturated sites seem to disappear after sulphurization whatever to be the nature of the reagents used or the amount of sulphur fixed. The amount of sulphur fixed on treatment with aqueous hydrogen sulphide at ordinary temperatures, in fact, was found to be almost exactly equivalent to the amount of surface unsaturation present initially in the carbon black (i.e., 1 sulphur atom ≡ two bromine atoms). These observations indicate that unsaturated sites are involved definitely in the fixation of sulphur. It is probably these sites which account for the unpaired spin centres where fixation of sulphur by an addition process has been considered likely by Blayden and Patrick¹⁰ in the case of carbons obtained from high polymers. The rest of the sulphur as obtained by subtracting the amounts taken as fixed at the unsaturated sites (equivalent to surface unsaturation as mentioned above) from the total amount of sulphur fixed is shown separately in parentheses in the appropriate columns of Table 1. In order to consider the mechanism of fixation of this portion of combined sulphur, the values obtained in the case of 1000°-outgassed carbons (which were

TABLE I. FIXATION OF SULPHUR ON VARIOUS CARBON BLACKS ON TREATMENT WITH VARIOUS SULPHURIZING REAGENTS AT 600°

Sample*	Surface Area (Nitrogen)	Sulphur fixed on treatment at 600° with		
		Sulphur vapour (mg.atom/g.)	Carbon disulphide vapour (mg.atom/g.)	Hydrogen Sulphide gas (mg.atom/g.)
<i>Mogul-A</i>				
A	228	4.12 (3.82)	3.15 (2.85)	1.82 (1.52)
B	251	3.32 (3.01)	1.80 (1.49)	1.38 (1.07)
C	241	2.58 (2.26)	1.34 (1.02)	0.86 (0.54)
<i>ELF-0</i>				
A	171	2.95 (2.76)	2.02 (1.83)	1.30 (1.11)
B	183	2.40 (2.20)	1.07 (0.87)	0.84 (0.64)
C	180	2.02 (1.83)	0.82 (0.63)	0.56 (0.37)
<i>Spheron-4</i>				
A	152	3.04 (2.75)	2.25 (1.96)	1.35 (1.06)
B	151	2.23 (1.93)	1.20 (0.90)	1.06 (0.76)
C	154	1.64 (1.32)	0.88 (0.56)	0.56 (0.24)
<i>Spheron-9</i>				
A	116	2.50 (2.20)	1.76 (1.47)	1.27 (0.98)
B	120	1.98 (1.71)	1.44 (1.17)	0.79 (0.52)
C	122	1.42 (1.19)	0.75 (0.45)	0.50 (0.20)
<i>Philblack-0</i>				
A	80	1.22 (1.02)	0.82 (0.62)	0.65 (0.45)
B	84	0.88 (0.66)	0.63 (0.41)	0.56 (0.34)
C	80	0.76 (0.54)	0.49 (0.27)	0.39 (0.17)
<i>Philblack-1</i>				
A	117	1.45 (1.27)	0.98 (0.80)	0.62 (0.44)
B	121	1.18 (0.98)	0.67 (0.47)	0.43 (0.23)
C	118	1.04 (0.86)	0.59 (0.41)	0.33 (0.15)
<i>Philblack-A</i>				
A	46	0.96 (0.80)	0.72 (0.56)	0.55 (0.39)
B	43	0.67 (0.47)	0.48 (0.28)	0.32 (0.12)
C	44	0.55 (0.37)	0.33 (0.15)	0.25 (0.07)

The values given in the parentheses were obtained after subtracting the sulphur fixed at the unsaturated sites.

* A—original sample; B—700°-outgassed sample; C—1000°-outgassed sample.

essentially free of oxygen), on treatment with various reagents, were considered first and plotted against corresponding specific surface areas in Fig. 3. It is seen that most of the points fit on a straight line for a given treatment, indicating a significant relationship between the two quantities. It appears likely that in these samples sulphur is fixed directly on the carbon surface forming stable C = S covalent bonds. It can be seen from the slope of each linear relationship that 0.92, 0.37 and 0.20 millig. atoms of sulphur are fixed per 100 m² of surface on treatment at 600° with sulphur vapour, carbon disulphide vapour, and hydrogen sulphide gas, respectively. Assuming that one atom of sulphur is fixed per active surface carbon atom occupying 8.3 Å² of the surface^{11,12}, it can be shown that only about 45, 18 and 10 per cent of the total surface carbon atoms are involved in the fixation of sulphur on treatment with the above reagents, in order of their mention, under optimum conditions.

It will be seen on reference to Table I that the original and 700°-outgassed carbons can fix more

Fig. 3.

Sulphur fixed on 1000°-outgassed carbons by a process other than addition in relation to surface area on treatment with sulphur (O—O), carbon disulphide (●—●) and hydrogen sulphide (▲—▲).

sulphur than the corresponding 1000°-outgassed samples can do. Since the former category of carbons are associated with oxygen and also more of hydrogen, it appears likely that the additional amount is fixed in these cases through interaction with oxy- or oxy-hydrogen groups present initially on the surface. In order to get some insight into this phenomenon, the additional sulphur fixed on these samples was plotted against the corresponding (i) hydrogen content, (ii) oxygen content evolved as carbon dioxide (CO₂-complex), and (iii) oxygen content evolved as carbon monoxide (CO-complex) in Figs. 4, 5 and 6,

and quinonic groups, it appears highly likely that it is these groups which are substituted during each reaction, yielding thiophenolic and thioquinonic structures.

In view of the above discussion, there appears to be three distinct categories of sites and mechanisms which, between themselves, can account for the total fixation of sulphur on carbon blacks.

Stability of carbon-sulphur surface complex: In order to determine the stability of the carbon-sulphur complex, the various sulphurized products were heated

Fig. 4.

Additional sulphur fixed on original carbon blacks in relation to hydrogen content on treatment with sulphur (○—○), carbon disulphide (●—●) and hydrogen sulphide (▲—▲).

respectively. As can be seen there is no valid relationship in the first two cases, since nearly the same amount of sulphur is fixed for appreciable variations in the values of hydrogen, or oxygen content present as CO₂-complex. The relationship

in a current of nitrogen (2½ hr) at different temperatures upto 1000°. The combined sulphur started coming off only above 600° as hydrogen sulphide.

Fig. 5.

Additional sulphur fixed on original carbon blacks in relation to oxygen evolved as carbon dioxide (CO₂-complex) on treatment with sulphur (○—○), carbon disulphide (●—●) and hydrogen sulphide (▲—▲).

with oxygen content present as CO-complex, however, seems to be quite significant as the points, for each reaction, fit fairly well on a straight line. Since this oxygen is known to be present as phenolic

Fig. 6.

Additional sulphur fixed on original carbon blacks in relation to oxygen evolved as carbon monoxide (CO-complex) on treatment with sulphur (○—○), carbon disulphide (●—●) and hydrogen sulphide (▲—▲).

carbon disulphide and free sulphur. The amount evolved of each of these species increased with rise in the temperature. At 1000°, nearly half of the combined sulphur came off as carbon disulphide and the rest as hydrogen sulphide and free sulphur.

The liberation of such appreciable amounts of carbon disulphide suggests the existence of strong valence forces, binding sulphur to surface carbon atoms such that when sulphur is desorbed it can tear off some of the underlying carbon atoms as well.

Oxidation of combined sulphur: The treatment of a sulphurized product (0.5 g.) with 50 ml. of 0.2 M aqueous bromine (with Br_2/Br' ratio equal to 1:3) could bring nearly 20 per cent of the combined sulphur in solution as sulphuric acid. The recovery of a small but significant fraction of the combined sulphur as sulphuric acid on treatment with such a mild oxidising agent as aqueous bromine appears to be due to the presence of thiophenol structures which are known to be readily oxidisable¹³. The elemental sulphur, it may be noted, cannot be oxidised by this reagent at all. The recovery of sulphur on treatment with excess of concentrated nitric acid (15 ml./g.) at 110° amounted to about 50 per cent. This suggests again that sulphur is not held in elemental state as a polymer because in that case the entire amount would have readily passed off as sulphuric under such a drastic treatment.

Another evidence in favour of chemisorption was obtained by studying the sodium azide-iodine reaction. It is well known^{7,10} that this reaction is catalysed by combined sulphur, soluble or insoluble, organic or inorganic, but not by free sulphur. The progress of the reaction, as measured by the amount of nitrogen evolved after different intervals of time, in the presence of 0.1 g. of a sample of Mogul-A or Spheron-4 (outgassed at 700°) before and after fixation of different amounts of sulphur, are plotted in Figs. 7 and 8 respectively. It is seen that a carbon

Fig. 7.

Rate of sodium azide-iodine reaction in the presence of 700°-outgassed Mogul-A before (□-□) and after fixation of sulphur on treatment with sulphur (○-○), carbon disulphide (●-●) and hydrogen sulphide (▲-▲).

black can catalyse this reaction only after fixation of sulphur. The catalytic activity is seen to increase with

increase in the amount of sulphur fixed. Thus, when Mogul-A, associated with 3.32 millig. atoms of sulphur

Fig. 8.

Rate of sodium azide-iodine reaction in the presence of 700°-outgassed Spheron-4 before (□-□) and after fixation of sulphur on treatment with sulphur (○-○), carbon disulphide (●-●) and hydrogen sulphide (▲-▲).

is used, the reaction becomes extremely fast and is carried to near completion, within 3 hr or so of the commencement of the reaction. These observations further support the view that sulphur fixed by carbons is held by chemical bonds.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (B.C.K.) is thankful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of Senior Research Fellowship.

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